

Smarandache Curves and Applications According to Type-2 Bishop Frame in Euclidean 3-Space

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Abstract: In this paper, we investigate Smarandache curves according to type-2 Bishop frame in Euclidean 3- space and we give some differential geometric properties of Smarandache curves. Also, some characterizations of Smarandache breadth curves in Euclidean 3- space are presented. Besides, we illustrate examples of our results.

Key Words: Smarandache curves, Bishop frame, curves of constant breadth.

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§1. Introduction

A regular curve in Euclidean 3-space, whose position vector is composed by Frenet frame vectors on another regular curve, is called a Smarandache curve. M. Turgut and S. Yılmaz have defined a special case of such curves and call it Smarandache TB_2 curves in the space E_1^4 [10]. Moreover, special Smarandache curves have been investigated by some differential geometric [6]. A.T.Ali has introduced some special Smarandache curves in the Euclidean space [2]. Special Smarandache curves according to Sabban frame have been studied by [5]. Besides, It has been determined some special Smarandache curves E_1^3 by [12]. Curves of constant breadth were introduced by L.Euler [3].

We investigate position vector of curves and some characterizations case of constant breadth according to type-2 Bishop frame in E^3 .

§2. Preliminaries

The Euclidean 3-space E^3 proved with the standard flat metric given by

$$\langle, \rangle = dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + dx_3^2$$

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where (x_1, x_2, x_3) is rectangular coordinate system of E^3 . Recall that, the norm of an arbitrary vector $a \in E^3$ given by $\|a\| = \sqrt{\langle a, a \rangle}$. φ is called a unit speed curve if velocity vector v of φ satisfied $\|v\| = 1$

The Bishop frame or parallel transport frame is alternative approach to defining a moving frame that is well defined even when the curve has vanishing second derivative. One can express parallel transport of orthonormal frame along a curve simply by parallel transporting each component of the frame [8]. The type-2 Bishop frame is expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \xi_1' \\ \xi_2' \\ B' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -\varepsilon_1 \\ 0 & 0 & -\varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_1 & \varepsilon_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 \\ \xi_2 \\ B \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.1)$$

In order to investigate type-2 Bishop frame relation with Serret-Frenet frame, first we

$$B' = -\tau N = \varepsilon_1 \xi_1 + \varepsilon_2 \xi_2 \quad (2.2)$$

Taking the norm of both sides, we have

$$\kappa(s) = \frac{d\theta(s)}{ds}, \quad \tau(s) = \sqrt{\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2} \quad (2.3)$$

Moreover, we may express

$$\varepsilon_1(s) = -\tau \cos \theta(s), \quad \varepsilon_2(s) = -\tau \sin \theta(s) \quad (2.4)$$

By this way, we conclude $\theta(s) = \text{Arc tan } \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_1}$. The frame $\{\xi_1, \xi_2, B\}$ is properly oriented, and τ and $\theta(s) = \int_0^s \kappa(s) ds$ are polar coordinates for the curve $\alpha(s)$.

We write the tangent vector according to frame $\{\xi_1, \xi_2, B\}$ as

$$T = \sin \theta(s) \xi_1 - \cos \theta(s) \xi_2$$

and differentiate with respect to s

$$\begin{aligned} T' = \kappa N = & \theta'(s)(\cos \theta(s) \xi_1 + \sin \theta(s) \xi_2) \\ & + \sin \theta(s) \xi_1' - \cos \theta(s) \xi_2' \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Substituting $\xi_1' = -\varepsilon_1 B$ and $\xi_2' = -\varepsilon_2 B$ in equation (2.5) we have

$$\kappa N = \theta'(s)(\cos \theta(s) \xi_1 + \sin \theta(s) \xi_2)$$

In the above equation let us take $\theta'(s) = \kappa(s)$. So we immediately arrive at

$$N = \cos \theta(s) \xi_1 + \sin \theta(s) \xi_2$$

Considering the obtained equations, the relation matrix between Serret-Frenet and the type-2 Bishop frame can be expressed

$$\begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta(s) & -\cos \theta(s) & 0 \\ \cos \theta(s) & \sin \theta(s) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 \\ \xi_2 \\ B \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

§3. Smarandache Curves According to Type-2 Bishop Frame in E^3

Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a unit speed regular curve in E^3 and denote by $\{\xi_1^\alpha, \xi_2^\alpha, B^\alpha\}$ the moving Bishop frame along the curve α . The following Bishop formulae is given by

$$\dot{\xi}_1^\alpha = -\varepsilon_1^\alpha B^\alpha, \quad \dot{\xi}_2^\alpha = -\varepsilon_2^\alpha B^\alpha, \quad \dot{B}^\alpha = \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha$$

3.1 $\xi_1 \xi_2$ -Smarandache Curves

Definition 3.1 Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a unit speed regular curve in E^3 and $\{\xi_1^\alpha, \xi_2^\alpha, B^\alpha\}$ be its moving Bishop frame. $\xi_1 \xi_2$ -Smarandache curves can be defined by

$$\beta(s^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\xi_1^\alpha + \xi_2^\alpha) \quad (3.1)$$

Now, we can investigate Bishop invariants of $\xi_1 \xi_2$ -Smarandache curves according to $\alpha = \alpha(s)$. Differentiating (3.1.1) with respect to s , we get

$$\dot{\beta} = \frac{d\beta}{ds^*} \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)B^\alpha \quad (3.2)$$

$$T_\beta \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)B^\alpha$$

where

$$\frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \quad (3.3)$$

The tangent vector of curve β can be written as follow;

$$T_\beta = -B^\alpha = -(\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha) \quad (3.4)$$

Differentiating (3.4) with respect to s , we obtain

$$\frac{dT_\beta}{ds^*} \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting (3.3) in (3.5), we get

$$T_\beta^\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha} (\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha)$$

Then, the curvature and principal normal vector field of curve β are respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} \|T_\beta^\alpha\| &= \kappa_\beta = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha} \sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2} \\ N_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} (\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we express

$$B_\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} \det \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1^\alpha & \xi_2^\alpha & B^\alpha \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ \varepsilon_1^\alpha & \varepsilon_2^\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

So, the binormal vector of curve β is

$$B_\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} (\varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha)$$

We differentiate (3.2)₁ with respect to s in order to calculate the torsion of curve β

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\beta} &= \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} \{ [(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha] \dot{\xi}_1^\alpha \\ &\quad + [\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2] \dot{\xi}_2^\alpha + [\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] B^\alpha \} \end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\ddot{\beta} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} (\delta_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \delta_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \delta_3 B^\alpha)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_1 &= 3\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + 2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^3 - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \varepsilon_2^\alpha \\ \delta_2 &= 2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + 3\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 - (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^3 \\ \delta_3 &= \ddot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha \end{aligned}$$

The torsion of curve β is

$$\tau_\beta = \frac{\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha}{4\sqrt{2}[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]} \{ [(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)(\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2)] \delta_1 - [(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)((\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha)] \delta_2 \}$$

3.2 $\xi_1 B$ -Smarandache Curves

Definition 3.2 Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a unit speed regular curve in E^3 and $\{\xi_1^\alpha, \xi_2^\alpha, B^\alpha\}$ be its moving

Bishop frame. $\xi_1 B$ -Smarandache curves can be defined by

$$\beta(s^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\xi_1^\alpha + B^\alpha) \quad (3.6)$$

Now, we can investigate Bishop invariants of $\xi_1 B$ -Smarandache curves according to $\alpha = \alpha(s)$. Differentiating (3.6) with respect to s , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\beta} &= \frac{d\beta}{ds^*} \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}(\varepsilon_1^\alpha B^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha) \\ T_\beta \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} &= \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}(-\varepsilon_1^\alpha B^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$\frac{ds^*}{ds} = \sqrt{\frac{2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}{2}} \quad (3.8)$$

The tangent vector of curve β can be written as follow;

$$T_\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}}(\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha B^\alpha) \quad (3.9)$$

Differentiating (3.9) with respect to s , we obtain

$$\frac{dT_\beta}{ds^*} \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{1}{[2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}}(\mu_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \mu_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \mu_3 B^\alpha) \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1 &= \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \\ \mu_2 &= 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - 2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^3 \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^3 \\ \mu_3 &= \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^4 + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 (\dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha)^2 - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting (3.8) in (3.10), we have

$$T_\beta^1 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{[2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^2}(\mu_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \mu_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \mu_3 B^\alpha)$$

Then, the first curvature and principal normal vector field of curve β are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \|T_\beta^1\| &= \kappa_\beta = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{[2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^2} \sqrt{\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + \mu_3^2} \\ N_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + \mu_3^2}}(\mu_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \mu_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \mu_3 B^\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we get

$$B_\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + \mu_3^2} \sqrt{2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} [(\mu_2 \varepsilon_1^\alpha + \mu_3 \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \xi_1^\alpha - (\mu_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \mu_3 \xi_1^\alpha) \xi_2^\alpha + (\mu_2 \varepsilon_1^\alpha - \mu_1 \varepsilon_2^\alpha) B^\alpha]$$

We differentiate (3.7) with respect to s in order to calculate the torsion of curve β

$$\ddot{\beta} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} \{ [-2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha] \xi_1^\alpha + [-\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2] \xi_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha B^\alpha \}$$

and similarly

$$\ddot{\beta} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \Gamma_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \Gamma_3 B^\alpha)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_1 &= -6\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \ddot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^3 \\ \Gamma_2 &= -2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - 2\varepsilon_2^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^3 \\ \Gamma_3 &= -\ddot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \end{aligned}$$

The torsion of curve β is

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_\beta &= -\frac{[2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^4}{4\sqrt{2}(\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + \mu_3^2)} \{ [(-\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2) \Gamma_1 \\ &\quad - 2((\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha) \Gamma_2 + (-\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2) \Gamma_3] \varepsilon_1^\alpha \\ &\quad - [(\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2) \Gamma_3 + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \Gamma_1] \varepsilon_2^\alpha \} \end{aligned}$$

3.3 $\xi_2 B$ -Smarandache Curves

Definition 3.3 Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a unit speed regular curve in E^3 and $\{\xi_1^\alpha, \xi_2^\alpha, B^\alpha\}$ be its moving Bishop frame. $\xi_2 B$ -Smarandache curves can be defined by

$$\beta(s^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\xi_2^\alpha + B^\alpha) \quad (3.11)$$

Now, we can investigate Bishop invariants of $\xi_2 B$ -Smarandache curves according to $\alpha = \alpha(s)$. Differentiating (3.11) with respect to s , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\beta} &= \frac{d\beta}{ds^*} \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = (-\varepsilon_2^\alpha B^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha) \\ T_\beta \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} &= (\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^\alpha B^\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

where

$$\frac{ds^*}{ds} = \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}{2}} \quad (3.13)$$

The tangent vector of curve β can be written as follow;

$$T_\beta = \frac{\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^\alpha B^\alpha}{\sqrt{2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} \quad (3.14)$$

Differentiating (3.14) with respect to s , we obtain

$$\frac{dT_\beta}{ds^*} \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{1}{\left[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} (\eta_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \eta_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \eta_3 B^\alpha) \quad (3.15)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1 &= 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \\ \eta_2 &= (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha \\ \eta_3 &= (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \varepsilon_2^\alpha + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^3 - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^4 - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^4 - 3(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting (3.13) in (3.15), we have

$$T_\beta^i = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\left[2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^2} (\eta_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \eta_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \eta_3 B^\alpha)$$

Then, the first curvature and principal normal vector field of curve β are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \|T_\beta^i\| &= \kappa_\beta = \frac{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2}}{\left[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^2} \\ N_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2}} (\eta_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \eta_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \eta_3 B^\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we express

$$\begin{aligned} B_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2} \sqrt{(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2}} [(\eta_2 \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \eta_3 \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \xi_1^\alpha \\ &\quad - (\eta_1 \xi_2^\alpha + \eta_3 \xi_1^\alpha) \xi_2^\alpha + (\eta_2 \varepsilon_1^\alpha - \eta_1 \varepsilon_2^\alpha) B^\alpha] \end{aligned}$$

We differentiate (3.12)₁ with respect to s in order to calculate the torsion of curve β

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\beta} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \{ [\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\xi}_1^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2] \xi_1^\alpha \\ &\quad + [\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\xi}_2^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2] \xi_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha B^\alpha \} \end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\ddot{\beta} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\eta_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \eta_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \eta_3 B^\alpha)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_1 &= -\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - 5\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \ddot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^3 \\ \eta_2 &= -4\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + 2\varepsilon_2^\alpha \\ \eta_3 &= -\ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha\end{aligned}$$

The torsion of curve β is

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_\beta &= -\frac{[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^{14}}{4\sqrt{2}(\eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2)} \{ [\varepsilon_2^\alpha \eta_2 + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2) \eta_3] \varepsilon_1^\alpha \\ &\quad + [2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \eta_1 + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2) \eta_2 \\ &\quad + (-\varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha) \eta_3] \varepsilon_2^\alpha \}\end{aligned}$$

3.4 $\xi_1 \xi_2 B$ -Smarandache Curves

Definition 3.4 Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a unit speed regular curve in E^3 and $\{\xi_1^\alpha, \xi_2^\alpha, B^\alpha\}$ be its moving Bishop frame. $\xi_1^\alpha \xi_2 B$ -Smarandache curves can be defined by

$$\beta(s^*) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(\xi_1^\alpha + \xi_2^\alpha + B^\alpha) \quad (3.16)$$

Now, we can investigate Bishop invariants of $\xi_1^\alpha \xi_2 B$ -Smarandache curves according to $\alpha = \alpha(s)$. Differentiating (3.16) with respect to s , we get

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\beta} &= \frac{d\beta}{ds^*} \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)B^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha] \\ T_\beta \cdot \frac{ds^*}{ds} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)B^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha]\end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

where

$$\frac{ds^*}{ds} = \sqrt{\frac{2[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]}{3}} \quad (3.18)$$

The tangent vector of curve β can be written as follow;

$$T_\beta = \frac{\varepsilon_1^\alpha \xi_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha \xi_2^\alpha - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)B^\alpha}{\sqrt{2[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]}} \quad (3.19)$$

Differentiating (3.19) with respect to s , we get

$$\frac{dT_\beta}{ds^*} \frac{ds^*}{ds} = \frac{(\lambda_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \lambda_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \lambda_3 B^\alpha)}{2\sqrt{2} \left[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (3.20)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= [\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] u(s) - \varepsilon_1^\alpha [2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + 2\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] \\ \lambda_2 &= [\dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] u(s) - \varepsilon_2^\alpha [\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + 2\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] \\ \lambda_3 &= [-\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] u(s) + \varepsilon_1^\alpha [2\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + 3\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + 2\varepsilon_2^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] \\ &\quad + \varepsilon_2^\alpha [\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2] \end{aligned}$$

Substituting (3.18) in (3.20), we have

$$T_\beta' = \frac{\sqrt{3}(\lambda_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \lambda_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \lambda_3 B^\alpha)}{4 \left[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^2}$$

Then, the first curvature and principal normal vector field of curve β are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \|T_\beta'\| &= \kappa_\beta = \frac{\sqrt{3} \sqrt{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2}}{4 \left[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \right]^2} \\ N_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2}} (\lambda_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \lambda_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \lambda_3 B^\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (3.21)$$

On the other hand, we express

$$B_\beta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]} \cdot \sqrt{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2}} \det \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1^\alpha & \xi_2^\alpha & B^\alpha \\ \varepsilon_1^\alpha & \varepsilon_2^\alpha & -(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \\ \lambda_1 & \lambda_2 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, the binormal vector field of curve β is

$$\begin{aligned} B_\beta &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]} \cdot \sqrt{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2}} \{ [(\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \lambda_1 \\ &\quad - \varepsilon_2^\alpha \lambda_3] \xi_1^\alpha + [-\varepsilon_1^\alpha \lambda_3 - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^\alpha)] \xi_2^\alpha + [\varepsilon_1^\alpha \lambda_2 - \varepsilon_2^\alpha \lambda_1] B^\alpha \} \end{aligned}$$

We differentiate (3.20) with respect to s in order to calculate the torsion of curve β

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\beta} &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \{ [2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\xi}_1^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha] \xi_1^\alpha \\ &\quad + [2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\xi}_2^\alpha - \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] \xi_2^\alpha + [\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha + \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha] B^\alpha \} \end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\beta = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(\sigma_1 \xi_1^\alpha + \sigma_2 \xi_2^\alpha + \sigma_3 B^\alpha)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_1 &= 4\dot{\varepsilon}_1^\alpha \varepsilon_1^\alpha + 3\varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^{\ddot{\alpha}} - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^3 - (\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 \varepsilon_2^\alpha \\ \eta_2 &= 5\dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \dot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^{\ddot{\alpha}} - 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^3 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 \\ \eta_3 &= \ddot{\varepsilon}_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_2^{\ddot{\alpha}}\end{aligned}$$

The torsion of curve β is

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_\beta &= -\frac{16[(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + (\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2]^2}{9\sqrt{3}\sqrt{\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2}} \{ [(2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^{\dot{\alpha}}) \sigma_1 + (-\varepsilon_2^{\dot{\alpha}} - 2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha) \sigma_2 \\ &\quad + (2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_2^{\dot{\alpha}}) \sigma_3] \varepsilon_1^\alpha + [-\varepsilon_1^{\dot{\alpha}} - 2\varepsilon_2^{\dot{\alpha}} + 2(\varepsilon_2^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha] \sigma_1 \\ &\quad + (-2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 - \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha + \varepsilon_1^{\dot{\alpha}}) \sigma_2 + (2(\varepsilon_1^\alpha)^2 + \varepsilon_1^\alpha \varepsilon_2^\alpha - \varepsilon_1^{\dot{\alpha}}) \sigma_3 \} \varepsilon_2^\alpha.\end{aligned}$$

§4. Smarandache Breadth Curves According to Type-2 Bishop Frame in E^3

A regular curve with more than 2 breadths in Euclidean 3-space is called Smarandache breadth curve.

Let $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ be a Smarandache breadth curve. Moreover, let us suppose $\alpha = \alpha(s)$ simple closed space-like curve in the space E^3 . These curves will be denoted by (C) . The normal plane at every point P on the curve meets the curve at a single point Q other than P .

We call the point Q the opposite point P . We consider a curve in the class Γ as in having parallel tangents ξ_1 and ξ_1^* opposite directions at opposite points α and α^* of the curves.

A simple closed curve having parallel tangents in opposite directions at opposite points can be represented with respect to type-2 Bishop frame by the equation

$$\alpha^*(s) = \alpha(s) + \lambda \xi_1 + \varphi \xi_2 + \eta B \quad (4.1)$$

where $\lambda(s)$, $\varphi(s)$ and $\eta(s)$ are arbitrary functions also α and α^* are opposite points.

Differentiating both sides of (4.1) and considering type-2 Bishop equations, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\alpha^*}{ds} = \xi_1^* \frac{ds^*}{ds} &= \left(\frac{d\lambda}{ds} + \eta \varepsilon_1 + 1 \right) \xi_1 + \left(\frac{d\varphi}{ds} + \eta \varepsilon_2 \right) \xi_2 \\ &\quad + \left(-\lambda \varepsilon_1 - \varphi \varepsilon_2 + \frac{d\eta}{ds} \right) B\end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Since $\xi_1^* = -\xi_1$ rewriting (4.2) we have

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\lambda}{ds} &= -\eta\varepsilon_1 - 1 - \frac{ds^*}{ds} \\ \frac{d\varphi}{ds} &= -\varphi\varepsilon_2 \\ \frac{d\eta}{ds} &= \lambda\varepsilon_1 + \varphi\varepsilon_2\end{aligned}\quad (4.3)$$

If we call θ as the angle between the tangent of the curve (C) at point $\alpha(s)$ with a given direction and consider $\frac{d\theta}{ds} = \kappa$, we have (4.3) as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d\lambda}{d\theta} &= -\eta\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} - f(\theta) \\ \frac{d\varphi}{d\theta} &= -\varphi\frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} \\ \frac{d\eta}{d\theta} &= \lambda\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} + \varphi\frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa}\end{aligned}\quad (4.4)$$

where $f(\theta) = \delta + \delta^*$, $\delta = \frac{1}{\kappa}$, $\delta^* = \frac{1}{\kappa^*}$ denote the radius of curvature at α and α^* respectively. And using system (4.4), we have the following differential equation with respect to λ as

$$\begin{aligned}&\frac{d^3\lambda}{d\theta^3} - \left[\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right]\frac{d^2\lambda}{d\theta^2} + \left[\frac{\varepsilon_1^2}{\kappa^2} - \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} - \frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\right)\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right]\frac{d\lambda}{d\theta} + \left[\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right) - \frac{\varepsilon_1^2}{\varepsilon_2\kappa}\right]\lambda + \\ &\quad + \left[-\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_2} - \frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right]\frac{d^2f}{d\theta^2} - \left[\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_2} + 2\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right]\frac{df}{d\theta} \\ &\quad - \left[\frac{\varepsilon_2^2}{\varepsilon_1\kappa} + \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_2} + 2\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\right)\frac{d}{d\theta}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right) + \frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1}\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2}\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa}\right)\right]f(\theta) = 0\end{aligned}\quad (4.5)$$

Equation (4.5) is characterization for α^* . If the distance between opposite points of (C) and (C^*) is constant, then we can write that

$$\|\alpha^* - \alpha\| = \lambda^2 + \varphi^2 + \eta^2 = l^2 = \text{constant}\quad (4.6)$$

Hence, we write

$$\lambda\frac{d\lambda}{d\theta} + \varphi\frac{d\varphi}{d\theta} + \eta\frac{d\eta}{d\theta} = 0\quad (4.7)$$

Considering system (4.4) we obtain

$$\lambda \cdot f(\theta) = 0\quad (4.8)$$

We write $\lambda = 0$ or $f(\theta) = 0$. Thus, we shall study in the following subcases.

Case 1. $\lambda = 0$. Then we obtain

$$\eta = -\int_0^\theta \frac{\kappa}{\varepsilon_1} f(\theta) d\theta, \quad \varphi = \int_0^\theta \left(\int_0^\theta \eta \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} d\theta \right) \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} d\theta \quad (4.9)$$

and

$$\frac{d^2 f}{d\theta^2} - \frac{df}{d\theta} - \left[\left(\frac{\tau}{\kappa} \right)^2 \frac{\sin^3 \theta}{\cos \theta} - \frac{\tau}{\kappa} \cos \theta \right] f = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

General solution of (4.10) depends on character of $\frac{\tau}{\kappa}$. Due to this, we distinguish following subcases.

Subcase 1.1 $f(\theta) = 0$. then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \int_0^\theta \eta \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} d\theta \\ \varphi &= -\int_0^\theta \eta \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} d\theta \\ \eta &= \int_0^\theta \lambda \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} d\theta + \int_0^\theta \varphi \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

Case 2. Let us suppose that $\lambda \neq 0$, $\varphi \neq 0$, $\eta \neq 0$ and λ , φ , η constant. Thus the equation (4.4) we obtain $\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\kappa} = 0$ and $\frac{\varepsilon_2}{\kappa} = 0$.

Moreover, the equation (4.5) has the form $\frac{d^3 \lambda}{d\theta^3} = 0$ The solution (4.12) is $\lambda = L_1 \frac{\theta^2}{2} + L_2 \theta + L_3$ where L_1 , L_2 and L_3 real numbers. And therefore we write the position vector and the curvature

$$\alpha^* = \alpha + A_1 \xi_1 + A_2 \xi_2 + A_3 B$$

where $A_1 = \lambda$, $A_2 = \varphi$ and $A_3 = \eta$ real numbers. And the distance between the opposite points of (C) and (C^*) is

$$\|\alpha^* - \alpha\| = A_1^2 + A_2^2 + A_3^2 = \text{constant}$$

§5. Examples

In this section, we show two examples of Smarandache curves according to Bishop frame in E^3 .

Example 5.1 First, let us consider a unit speed curve of E^3 by

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(s) = & \left(\frac{25}{306} \sin(9s) - \frac{9}{850} \sin(25s), \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{25}{306} \cos(9s) + \frac{9}{850} \cos(25s), \frac{15}{136} \sin(8s) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Fig.1 The curve $\beta = \beta(s)$

See the curve $\beta(s)$ in Fig.1. One can calculate its Serret-Frenet apparatus as the following

$$T = \left(\frac{25}{34} \cos 9s + \frac{9}{34} \cos 25s, \frac{25}{34} \sin 9s - \frac{9}{34} \sin 25s, \frac{15}{17} \cos 8s \right)$$

$$N = \left(\frac{15}{34} \csc 8s (\sin 9s - \sin 25s), -\frac{15}{34} \csc 8s (\cos 9s - \cos 25s), \frac{8}{17} \right)$$

$$B = \left(\frac{1}{34} (25 \sin 9s - 9 \sin 25s), -\frac{1}{34} (25 \cos 9s + 9 \cos 25s), -\frac{15}{17} \sin 8s \right)$$

$$\kappa = -15 \sin 8s \text{ and } \tau = 15 \cos 8s$$

In order to compare our main results with Smarandache curves according to Serret-Frenet frame, we first plot classical Smarandache curve of β Fig.1.

Now we focus on the type-2 Bishop trihedral. In order to form the transformation matrix (2.6), let us express

$$\theta(s) = - \int_0^s 15 \sin(8s) ds = \frac{15}{8} \cos(8s)$$

Since, we can write the transformation matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin\left(\frac{15}{8} \cos 8s\right) & -\cos\left(\frac{15}{8} \cos 8s\right) & 0 \\ \cos\left(\frac{15}{8} \cos 8s\right) & \sin\left(\frac{15}{8} \cos 8s\right) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \xi_1 \\ \xi_2 \\ B \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig.2 $\xi_1\xi_1$ Smarandache curve

By the method of Cramer, one can obtain type-2 Bishop frame of β as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 = & \left(\sin \theta \left(\frac{25}{34} \cos 9s - \frac{9}{34} \cos 25s \right) + \frac{15}{34} \cos \theta \csc 8s (\sin 9s - \sin 25s), \right. \\ & \left. \sin \theta \left(\frac{25}{34} \sin 9s - \frac{9}{34} \sin 25s \right) - \frac{15}{34} \cos \theta \csc 8s (\cos 9s - \cos 25s), \right. \\ & \left. \frac{15}{17} \sin \theta \cos 8s + \frac{8}{17} \cos \theta \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_2 = & \left(-\cos \theta \left(\frac{25}{34} \cos 9s - \frac{9}{34} \cos 25s \right) + \frac{15}{34} \sin \theta \csc 8s (\sin 9s - \sin 25s), \right. \\ & \left. -\cos \theta \left(\frac{25}{34} \sin 9s - \frac{9}{34} \sin 25s \right) - \frac{15}{34} \sin \theta \csc 8s (\cos 9s - \cos 25s), \right. \\ & \left. -\frac{15}{17} \cos \theta \cos 8s + \frac{8}{17} \sin \theta \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$B = \left(\frac{1}{34}(25 \sin 9s - 9 \sin 25s), -\frac{1}{34}(25 \cos 9s + 9 \cos 25s), -\frac{15}{17} \sin 8s \right)$$

where $\theta = \frac{15}{8} \cos(8s)$. So, we have Smarandache curves according to type-2 Bishop frame of the unit speed curve $\beta = \alpha(s)$, see Fig.2-4 and Fig.5.

Fig.3 ξ_1B Smarandache curve

Fig.5 $\xi_1 \xi_2 B$ Smarandache curve

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